

Service Quality Amidst Pandemic: An Assessment Towards Excellent Customer Satisfaction in Selected Fast-Food Establishment

Regine Macabenta¹, Kheeng Zerg Diane², Jerusalem Baranda³

^{1,2,3} Hotel and Restaurant Management Society, CTHM, De Las Salle University- Dasmariñas, Philippines

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Abstract: This study aims to assess the customer level satisfaction in selected fast-food establishments in Walter Mart Dasmariñas, Cavite at the time of pandemic as new normal guidelines is being considered. Safety measures have been mandated to different fast-food restaurants and strictly implemented. However, there may be nonconformities during operations due to reasons that are yet to be investigated and level of customer satisfaction is yet to be assessed. This study utilized survey questionnaires that was administered to randomly selected participants. The researchers randomly chose participants online to participate in this study. The use of technology through Google form was utilized in conducting this research since people are limited to go outside because the threat of covid-19 virus still exists. This study was significant because it will benefit the selected fast-food establishments to determine the level of customer satisfaction as this will be assessed in current study. Moreover, this will give them the factual assessment of their service quality considering its tangibility, reliability, responsiveness, assurance, and empathy that will be useful when they create their respective customer service guidelines based on the result of the study that leads to the improvement of their service quality in the new normal set up. The researchers presented recommendations to the selected fast-food restaurants to further improve their service quality.

Keywords: Customers Satisfaction, Customers Service, Recommendations, Safety Protocols, Service Quality.

I. INTRODUCTION

The tourism and hospitality industry is one of the most affected businesses when Covid -19 pandemic started in year 2020. Tourism and hospitality businesses are tremendously impacted both globally and locally and under this is the fast-food industry. Fast-food industry is one of the fastest-growing businesses and due to pandemic, the operations are affected because of the different protocols and guidelines being implemented. According to IATF Resolutions (2020), The IATF implemented a community Quarantine in the Philippines, and this was released since April 20, 2020, through resolution No.30 until now to control the spread of the virus.

The customers are used to going to these fast-food establishments and dining in or taking away their ordered food and enjoying their meals. However, due to pandemic, all these practices were changed in accordance with the Inter-Agency Task Force guidelines and policies. Strict compliance to these protocols shall be upheld by the fast-food establishments; hence, changes were met along the way. Quality of service is important to everyone. The establishment makes their customers wait for the time their orders are prepared and served even it takes a little longer, service quality is vital. This pandemic changed some rules inside the restaurant to ensure the safety of their customers, but still food quality, physical environment quality and employee service quality is significant to the customer to make them visit the establishment. (Neale J.S et al., 2020). Fast-food restaurants are negatively impacted because customers are limited to dine in due to the

restrictions by the government. Limited number of customers are allowed to go inside the establishment like limiting to 10% only are allowed during Modified Enhanced Community Quarantine (MECQ), 30% for General Community Quarantine (GCQ) areas and 50% capacity are allowed to dine in in Modified General Community Quarantine (MGCQ) areas. (IATF Resolutions.,2020). And, in this scenario customers comply, and fast-food restaurants are expected to conform as well to the safety protocols. According to Zoirova and Young-joo (2021), during this time of Pandemic when it comes communication and interaction are limited because customers are avoiding much contact to people as well as the service provider.

According to Dushica and Sonja (2018) The restaurant service makes customers satisfied when orders are delivered on time and when they always handle customers request. However, in this current situation where varieties of changes are being done and extra care is a must during restaurant operations, customer service is affected as well. It may be the span of time being spent in the process of taking orders, preparing the food, calling out the customers or delivering to them has changed. There is limited contact between crew persons and customers, hence, quality of individualized service is a question now.

II. RESEARCH BACKGROUND

The researchers came up with this study, they have first-hand experience. Two members of this research are former workers in Jollibee Food Corporation before and during the pandemic. But at some point, the researchers are assuring that the result of this research will be a hundred percent honest and bias judgment will be avoided. Researchers are observant to the things happening inside the restaurant, and the researchers became a customer also which experience some changes in their service because of the implemented new rules during new normal. This research will sustain the customers satisfaction and to reach out the customers service provider about their current customers level of satisfaction. Personal take in this research will not be comprised because the most important view in this research is the view of the customers towards the service they are experiencing in the new normal.

This study aimed to determine the service quality provided by different fast-food restaurants in Walter Mart Dasmariñas such as Kentucky Fried Chicken, Greenwich, Jollibee Food Corporation and McDonalds. This study purpose is to answer the following questions.

1.What is the demographic profile of the respondents in terms of:

1.1

Age

1.2 Gender

1.3 Current employment status

1.4 Marital Status

1.5 Educational Attainment

2.What is level service quality of selected Fast-food establishments in terms of:

2.1 Tangibility

2.2 Reliability

2.3 Responsiveness

2.4 Assurance

2.5 Empathy

3. Is there a significant difference in the customer service rating when grouped according to profile?

4. What customer service guidelines during pandemic can be proposed to the selected Fast-food establishments in Walter Mart Dasmariñas?

III. HYPOTHESIS

There is no significant difference between service quality and the profile of the respondents.

IV. LITERATURE REVIEW

According to Zoirova and Young-Joo (2021), During this time of Pandemic, communication and interaction are limited because customers are avoiding much contact to people as well as the service provider, they are wearing PPEs such as facemask, gloves, and face shield because this is mandated to them. Alcohols and sanitizers are in front of the counter and even beside the contact tracing table, and those practices make people feel that they are safe in the establishments. According to Neale (2020) Food quality, physical environment quality and employee service quality is significant to the customers to make them visit the establishment. But the environment during pandemic has been changed although the service quality is still a priority.

The restaurant service made customers be satisfied when it is on time and when they always handle their customers request. (Dushica and Sonja., 2018). Promise time or waiting time is given to the customers when the products are not yet available at the counter or kitchen. However, Customers who had low income considers more on packaging and promos than the safety of the foods. Service that made the customer satisfied and loyal to the restaurant is a service that will make them feel comfortable even the world is facing pandemic (Yogi T.P et al., 2021).

Customers visit fast food restaurants to stay then eat, and for them quality of the service is important. The restaurant can make their customer wait for the promise time but just make sure that they cannot stand in this situation forever. The research instrument was created in basis of related literatures on service quality which was conducted by Macias. R., et al., (June 2021).

V. RESEARCH FRAMEWORK

In this study, the researchers are aims to determine the assessment of the service quality and customer satisfaction in Fast-food establishments in Walter Mart Dasmariñas during pandemic since customers' expectations are high and to meet that service, provider will do the best service they can do. (Bharat et al., 2014) The fast-food restaurants considered in this research are Jollibee Food Corporation, Mc Donald's, Greenwich, and Kentucky Fried Chicken.

At the end of the study, this research aims to benefit the selected fast-food establishments to know if they successfully satisfy customer service. This study will help the said fast food restaurants to improve their service quality or to commend them on their great service.

VI. METHODOLOGY

This research utilized the survey questionnaire in gathering information about the topic at hand. This is the most appropriate method to use in this research since people had limited time to go outside, to follow safety protocols.

The study was conducted in different fast-food restaurant specifically Jollibee, KFC, McDonalds, and Greenwich in Walter Mart Dasmariñas city, Cavite. The researcher aimed to know the customer satisfaction of the stated fast-food establishments in which the participants included are those who have experienced to dine in this specific restaurant, the customers were contacted online and administered survey questionnaire via Google form.

John Lister (2011) discussed the kinds of different sampling method that used to gather and decide the target population. And this study used a simple random sampling to respondents to answer the provided survey questions. This sampling is the simplest popular and accurate to treat the survey questions. The information's from different sources been treated without any bias. The collected data has been analysed to know if the new normal customer services are. The number of participants is based on the number of daily transactions per establishment.

The researchers utilized Raosoft to determine the sample size. Based on the given information, for Fast-food no. 1, daily transaction count is 350, Fast-food no. 2 is 400, Fast-food no. 3 is 180 and Fast-food no. 4 is 150. Based on the computation, Fast-food no. 1 will need to gather 184 respondents, Fast-food no.2 is 197, Fast-food no. 3 is 123 and Fast-food is 109.

This study utilizes the Likert Scale to determine customer service satisfaction if they strongly disagree/Very low (1.00-1.49), disagree/low (1.50-2.49), agree/high (2.50-3.48) and strongly agree/very high (3.50-4.00).

Verbal Interpretation of the Mean

1.00-1.49	Strongly Disagree/Very Low
1.50-2.49	Disagree/Low
2.50-3.49	Agree/High
3.50-4.00	Strongly Agree/Very High

VII. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

1.What is the demographic profile of the respondents in terms of:

Table 1.1: Demographic profile of respondents in terms of Age

Age	Frequency	Percent
1- Below 18	15	5.282
2- 19-25	188	66.197
3- 26-32	52	18.31
4- 33-39	15	5.282
5 40-47	8	2.817
6 48-54	4	1.408
7 56-61	2	0.704
Total	284	100

The table shows that out of 284 respondents, most of them are age of 19 to 25 years old with a percentage of 66.197%. There are also other 52 respondents that are 26-32 years old, 15 respondents are 33-39 years old, 8 respondents are 40-47 years old, 4 respondents are 48-54 years old and 2 respondents from 56–61-year-old. The data implies that most of the respondents are in the age range of 19-25 years old, they belong to the young adult age group. This is the implication of the Inter Agency Task Force (2020) safety protocols that there is only one person per household who can go outside to buy essentials for the family and the survey says that the authorized person outside residence is more on young adults because below 18 years old and senior citizens are not allowed to go out of their homes.

Table 1.2: Demographic profile of respondents in terms of Gender

Gender	Frequency	Percent
1-Female	160	56.338
2-Male	124	43.662
Total	284	100

The table shows that 56.338% of the respondents are from female while 43.662% are male respondents. The data implies that there are more female respondents than male it can be because female more often buying food in the fast-food restaurant than males. According to Gabriela Ramos (2020) because of the widespread of the virus women are left at home to spend childcare and to supervise the schooling of their children while their husband is working, this shows that female had more time to buy food outside because of their husband is working.

Table 1.3: Demographic profile of respondents in terms of Current Employment Status

Occupation	Frequency	Percent
1-unemployed	103	36.268
2-Student	68	23.944
3-Housewife	11	3.873
4- Call Center Agent	25	8.803
5- Food Service	48	16.901
6- Others	29	10.211
Total	284	100

The table shows that out of 284 respondents 103 of them or the 36.268% are unemployed, while the other 68 respondent are student, 11 respondents are housewife, 25 respondents are Call center agent, 48 respondents are in Food service and the other or not specified occupation are 29 respondents. The data implies that most of the respondents are unemployed, because according to NEDA (2020) Last April 2020 the country recorded its lowest unemployment rate, when the covid 19 strikes in the Philippines, most of the people ended up jobless after the government declared the lockdown and quarantines and most of the customers are college students.

Table 1.4: Demographic profile of respondents in terms of Marital Status

Marital Status	Frequency	Percent
1-Single	243	85.563
2-Married	35	12.324
3-Widowed	2	0.704
4-Separated	3	1.056
5-Divorced	1	0.352
Total	284	100

The table shows the status of the respondents which is out of 284 respondents 243 of them are single, 35 of the respondents are married, 2 of them are widowed, 3 of them are separated and 1 of them is divorced. The data implied that most of the respondents are single because most of the respondents are in the young adult age and they are students. According to College Pulse (2021) College Students experiencing challenge on how to safely meet people during pandemic and that is the reason why they are staying not in a relationship in times of Pandemic.

Table 1.5: Demographic profile of respondents in terms of Educational Attainment

Educational Attainment	Frequency	Percent
1-Elementary level	2	0.704
2-Junior High School Level	31	10.915
3- Senior High School Level	59	20.775
4- College Level	192	67.606
Total	284	100

The table shows that out of 284 respondents' majority of them are 192 respondents from college level, 59 respondents from Senior high school level, 31 respondents from Junior high school level and 2 from elementary level. The data implies that most of the respondents are College levels, this shows that most of the customers of the fast-food restaurant during pandemic are college students. Because of the age range set by the Inter Agency Task Force (2020) that is allowed to go out of their home.

Table 1.6: Demographic profile of respondents in terms of Fast-Food restaurant

Fast Food restaurant	Frequency	Percent
1-KFC	70	24.648
2-Jollibee	72	25.352
3-McDonalds	71	25
4-Greenwich	71	25
Total	284	100

The table shows that 70(26.648%) respondents are from KFC, 72 (25.352%) from Jollibee, 71 (25%) from McDonalds and 71(25%) from Greenwich. The data implies that the four different fast-food had 70-72 respondents to see the level of service quality they provided in their customers.

2.What is the level of service quality of selected Fast-food establishments in terms of:

Table 2.1: level of service quality of selected Fast-food establishments in terms of Tangibility

Tangibility	Mean	Verbal Interpretation
Q1.1	3.609	Strongly agree
Q1.2	3.532	Strongly agree
Q1.3	3.518	Strongly agree
Q1.4	3.62	Strongly agree
Level of service quality in Terms of tangibility	3.57	Very High

The table shows that 3.609 of the mean in question number 1.1 is strongly agree as well as the questions 1.2 that is 3.532, the mean of question 1.3 is 3.518 and question 1.4 is 3.62 which interpreted that the level of service quality in terms of tangibility is very high with the total mean of 3.57. The data implies that the level of service quality in terms of tangibility are very high that the crew person had a clean and well-kept physical appearance, the ambiance of the facility is welcoming, all the Point of Service are functioning, and the crew persons are showing friendly hand gestures even they are wearing face mask. Therefore, the service quality of four fast-food in terms of tangibility made an excellent customer satisfaction to their customer during pandemic, even though the crew person needs to follow safety protocols of IATF (2020), and the communication and interaction are limited to avoid much contact to customers. (Zoirova & Young-Joo 2021)

Table 2.2: level of service quality of selected Fast-food establishments in terms of Reliability

Reliability	Mean	Verbal Interpretation
Q2.1	3.486	Agree
Q2.2	3.662	Strongly agree
Q2.3	3.528	Strongly agree
Level of Service quality in Terms of reliability	3.559	Very High

The table above shows that question 2.1 has 3.486 mean that has a verbal interpretation of agree, question 2.2 has 3.662 and question 2.3 that has 3.528 and has a verbal interpretation of strongly agree. The overall mean is 3.559, the level of service quality in terms of reliability is very high. The data implies that the level of service quality in terms of reliability are very high that the crew persons are assisting their customers in carrying their food and thing if needed, the workers are courteous and confident with the service that they are providing, and the delivery time of the food is appropriate in the time given. It shows that the crew person is reliable to the service they are providing, because according to Dushica and Sonja (2020) the restaurant service satisfies their customer when they are on time and when they always handle their customers request, Therefore, the four restaurants satisfy the customers in terms of reliability.

Table 2.3: level of service quality of selected Fast-food establishments in terms of Responsiveness

Responsiveness	Mean	Verbal Interpretation
Q3.1	3.599	Strongly agree
Q3.2	3.648	Strongly agree
Level of Service quality in Terms of responsiveness	3.623	Very High

The table above shows that question 3.1 has 3.599 mean and verbal interpretation of strongly agree and question 3.2 has 3.684 mean and verbal interpretation of strongly agree. The overall mean in responsiveness is 3.623, the level of service quality in terms of responsiveness is very high. The data implies that the level of service quality in terms of responsiveness are very high that the workers are responding quickly to the customers when they need something and the service quality that they are providing satisfies their customer. Therefore, the service quality of four fast-food in terms of responsiveness made an excellent customer satisfaction to their customer during pandemic, since it is significant to the customers the food quality, physical environment quality and employee service quality (Neale 2020).

Table 2.4: level of service quality of selected Fast-food establishments in terms of Assurance

Assurance	Mean	Verbal Interpretation
Q4.1	3.718	Strongly agree
Q4.2	3.641	Strongly agree
Q4.3	3.771	Strongly agree
Level of Service quality in Terms of assurance	3.71	Very High

The table shows that question 4.1 has 3.718 mean and verbal interpretation of strongly agree, question 4.2 has 3.641 of mean and verbal interpretation of strongly agree and question 4.3 has 3.771 mean and verbal interpretation of strongly agree, the overall mean in assurance is 3.71 which means that the level of service quality in terms of assurance is very high. The data implies that the level of service quality in terms of assurance are very high that the food was properly packed, the customers received the food in appropriate temperature and the smell of the food was tempting. Therefore, the service quality of four fast-food in terms of assurance made an excellent customer satisfaction to their customer during pandemic, the crew person assured that they handle the food excellently to the customers, because the smell of the food and the packaging of the food had an impact to their loyal customers. (Yogi T.P et al., 2021).

Table 2.5: Level of service quality of selected Fast-food establishments in terms of Empathy

Empathy	Mean	Verbal Interpretation
Q5.1	3.595	Strongly agree
Q5.2	3.62	Strongly agree
Level of Service quality in Terms of empathy	3.607	Very High

The table shows that question 5.1 has 3.595 mean and verbal interpretation of strongly agree and question 5.2 has 3.62 mean and verbal interpretation strongly agree the overall mean is 3.607 that means the level of service quality in terms of empathy is very high. The data implies that the level of service quality in terms of empathy are very high that the customers received the food at the appropriate time given and the customers are doing the clean as you go practices. The crew person successfully gives the best service they had in the restaurant because according to Macias et al (2021) the customers are going to fast-food restaurant to stay and eat, and the quality of service is important to them mostly when the crew person is on time when they are giving promise time to their customers. Therefore, the service quality of four fast-food in terms of empathy made an excellent customer satisfaction to their customer during pandemic.

3. Is there a significant difference in the customer service rating when grouped according to profile?

Table 3.1: Significant difference in the customer service rating when grouped according to age

Age	Tangibility	Reliability	Responsiveness	Assurance	Empathy	Overall
1- Below 18	3.55	3.667	3.833	3.711	3.733	3.699
2- 19-25	3.574	3.578	3.649	3.768	3.646	3.643
3- 26-32	3.644	3.551	3.577	3.647	3.558	3.596
4- 33-39	3.383	3.244	3.4	3.378	3.167	3.314
5 40-47	3.438	3.458	3.313	3.417	3.625	3.45
6 48-54	3.5	3.75	3.75	3.75	3.625	3.675
7 56-61	3.375	3.5	3.5	3.5	3.5	3.475
F-Value	0.813	1.358	1.503	3.53	1.965	1.957
p-value	0.56	0.232	0.177	0.002	0.071	0.072
Interpretation	Not Significant	Not Significant	Not Significant	Significant	Not Significant	Not Significant

Interpretation: There is no significant difference in the customer service rating specifically, tangibility, reliability, responsiveness, and empathy when respondents are grouped by age, since the F-values of 0.813, 1.353, 1.503 and 1.965 have p-values greater than 0.05. The null hypothesis of no significant difference is not rejected. Customers from different age groups have the same rating of, tangibility, reliability, responsiveness, and empathy.

However, there is a significant difference in the customer service rating in terms of assurance when respondents are grouped by age since the F-value of 3.53 has a p-value less than 0.05. The null hypothesis of no significant difference is rejected. Customers with age of 25 years and below has higher rating of assurance than older costumers.

Lastly, there is no significant difference in the overall customer service rating when respondents are grouped by age since the F-values of 1.957 has a p-value greater than 0.05. The null hypothesis of no significant difference is not rejected. Customers from different age groups have the same overall customer service rating.

Table 3.2: Significant difference in the customer service rating when grouped according to gender

Gender	Tangibility	Reliability	Responsiveness	Assurance	Empathy	Overall
Female	3.584	3.583	3.65	3.725	3.566	3.622
Male	3.55	3.527	3.589	3.691	3.661	3.604
t-Value	0.611	0.958	0.965	0.707	1.437	0.371
p-value	0.542	0.339	0.335	0.48	0.152	0.711
Interpretation	Not Significant					

Interpretation: There is no significant difference in the customer service rating specifically, tangibility, reliability, responsiveness, assurance, and empathy when respondents are grouped by gender, since the t-values of 0.611, 0.958, 0.965, 0.707, and 1.437 have p-values greater than 0.05. The null hypothesis of no significant difference is not rejected. Male and female Customers have the same rating of, tangibility, reliability, responsiveness, assurance, and empathy.

Lastly, there is no significant difference in the overall customer service rating when respondents are grouped by gender since the t-value of 0.371 has a p-value greater than 0.05. The null hypothesis of no significant difference is not rejected. Male and female customers have the same overall customer service rating.

Table 3.3: Significant difference in the customer service rating when grouped according to Occupation

Occupation	Tangibility	Reliability	Responsiveness	Assurance	Empathy	Overall
1-unemployed	3.617	3.657	3.704	3.764	3.777	3.704
2-Student	3.504	3.417	3.618	3.75	3.551	3.568
3-Housewife	3.818	3.697	3.545	3.848	3.455	3.673
4- Call Center	3.57	3.52	3.52	3.573	3.3	3.497
5- Food Service	3.578	3.583	3.635	3.646	3.573	3.603
6- Others	3.448	3.483	3.448	3.598	3.517	3.499
F-Value	1.53	2.372	1.358	2.065	4.126	2.156
p-value	0.18	0.04	0.24	0.07	0.001	0.059
Interpretation	Not Significant	Significant	Not Significant	Significant	Significant	Not Significant

Interpretation: There is no significant difference in the customer service rating specifically, tangibility, AND responsiveness when respondents are grouped by occupation since the F-values of 1.53 and 1.358 have p-values greater than 0.05. The null hypothesis of no significant difference is not rejected. Customers with different occupations have the same rating of tangibility and responsiveness.

However, there is a significant difference in the customer service rating in terms of reliability, assurance, and empathy when respondents are grouped by occupation, since the F-values of 2.372, 2.065 and 4.126 have p-values less than 0.05. The null hypothesis of no significant difference is rejected.

Lastly, there is no significant difference in the overall customer service rating when respondents are grouped by occupation since the F-value of 2.156 has a p-value greater than 0.05. The null hypothesis of no significant difference is not rejected. Customers with different occupation have the same overall customer service rating.

Table 3.4: Significant difference in the customer service rating when grouped according to Marital Status

Marital Status	Tangibility	Reliability	Responsiveness	Assurance	Empathy	Overall
Single	3.577	3.575	3.644	3.728	3.621	3.629
Married	3.529	3.448	3.471	3.6	3.514	3.512
Others	3.5	3.556	3.667	3.611	3.583	3.583
F-Value	0.235	1.019	1.646	1.745	0.569	1.284
p-value	0.791	0.362	0.195	0.177	0.567	0.279
Interpretation	Not Significant					

Interpretation: There is no significant difference in the customer service rating specifically, tangibility, reliability, responsiveness, assurance, and empathy when respondents are grouped by marital status, since the F-values of 0.235, 1.019, 1.646, 1.745 and 0.569 have p-values greater than 0.05. The null hypothesis of no significant difference is not rejected. Customers with different marital status have the same rating of tangibility, reliability, responsiveness, assurance, and empathy.

Lastly, there is no significant difference in the overall customer service rating when respondents are grouped by marital status since the F-values of 1.284 has a p-value greater than 0.05. The null hypothesis of no significant difference is not rejected. Customers with different marital status have the same overall customer service rating.

Table 3.5: Significant difference in the customer service rating when grouped according to Educational Attainment

Educational attainment	Tangibility	Reliability	Responsiveness	Assurance	Empathy	Overall
1-Elementary level	3	3.167	3.25	3.5	3.75	3.333
2-High School Level	3.653	3.656	3.645	3.763	3.645	3.673
3- Senior High School Level	3.572	3.667	3.661	3.723	3.78	3.681
4- College Level	3.561	3.514	3.612	3.7	3.547	3.587
F-Value	1.367	2.331	0.473	0.423	2.774	1.354
p-value	0.253	0.075	0.701	0.737	0.042	0.257
Interpretation	Not Significant	Not Significant	Not Significant	Not Significant	Significant	Not Significant

Interpretation: There is no significant difference in the customer service rating specifically, tangibility, reliability, responsiveness, and assurance when respondents are grouped by educational attainment, since the F-values of 1.367, 2.331, 0.473 and 0.423 have p-values greater than 0.05. The null hypothesis of no significant difference is not rejected. Customers with different educational attainment have the same rating of tangibility, reliability, responsiveness, and assurance.

However, there is a significant difference in the customer service rating specifically, empathy when respondents are grouped by educational attainment since the F-value 2.774 has a p-value less than 0.05. The null hypothesis of no significant difference is rejected.

Lastly, there is no significant difference in the overall customer service rating when respondents are grouped by educational attainment since the F-value of 1.354 has a p-value greater than 0.05. The null hypothesis of no significant difference is not rejected. Customers with different educational attainment have the same overall customer service rating.

Table 3.6: Significant difference in the customer service rating when grouped according to Fast-Food Restaurant

Educational attainment	Tangibility	Reliability	Responsiveness	Assurance	Empathy	Overall
1-KFC	3.6	3.667	3.757	3.743	3.786	3.71
2-Jollibee	3.549	3.505	3.521	3.694	3.451	3.544
3-McDonalds	3.563	3.507	3.549	3.648	3.556	3.565
4-Greenwich	3.567	3.559	3.669	3.756	3.641	3.638
F-Value	0.153	1.682	3.082	1.059	4.729	2.50
p-value	0.928	0.171	0.028	0.367	0.003	0.06
Interpretation	Not Significant	Not Significant	Significant	Not Significant	Significant	Not Significant

Interpretation: There is no significant difference in the customer service rating specifically, tangibility, reliability, and assurance when respondents are grouped by fast-food restaurant, since the F-values of 0.153, 1.682 and 1.059 have p-values greater than 0.05. The null hypothesis of no significant difference is not rejected. Customers from different fast-food restaurants have the same rating of, tangibility, reliability, and assurance.

However, there is a significant difference in the customer service rating specifically, responsiveness and empathy when respondents are grouped by fast-food restaurant since the F-values of 3.082 and 4.729 have p-values less than 0.05. The null hypothesis of no significant difference is rejected.

Lastly, there is no significant difference in the overall customer service rating when respondents are grouped by fast-food restaurant since the F-value of 2.50 has a p-value greater than 0.05. The null hypothesis of no significant difference is not rejected. Customers from different fast-food restaurant have the same overall customer service rating.

VIII. CONCLUSION

The study of the Service Quality Amidst Pandemic: An Assessment Towards Excellent Customer Satisfaction in Selected Fast-Food Establishment conducted by the researchers to assess the customers satisfaction in different fast-food establishment in Walter mart Dasmariñas, Cavite in Philippines.

The study was conducted to 284 respondents who participated in the research. We have categorized demographic profile of respondents such as age, gender, current employment status, marital status, and educational attainment. In terms of age most of the respondents are in the age range of 19-25 years old, they belong to the young adult age group. In terms of gender there are more female respondents than male it can be because female more often buying food in the fast-food restaurant than males. In terms of current employment status that most of the respondents are unemployed. In terms of marital status most of the respondents are single because most of the respondents are in the young adult age and students. And in terms of educational attainment most of the respondents are College levels. With this result therefore we conclude that the service quality of different fast-food in Walter Mart Dasmariñas City, Cavite specifically Kentucky Fried Chicken, Greenwich, McDonalds, and Jollibee Food Corporation is giving an excellent customer service satisfaction during pandemic.

Based on the findings of the researchers the demographic profile of the respondents in terms of age, gender, current employment status, marital status and educational attainment has no significant differences in the customers service rating in tangibility, reliability, responsiveness, assurance and empathy with their overall perceptions on the satisfaction of customers towards the service quality of the different fast-food establishment in Walter Mart Dasmariñas City, Cavite Philippines, The null hypothesis that no significant difference between service quality and the profile of respondents was not rejected.

This indicated that the demographic profile of the respondent did not affect the perceptions of the customers on their satisfaction in the service quality of the fast-food restaurants during pandemic.

The customers are generally strongly agreeing that the Jollibee, Greenwich, Kentucky Frid Chicken and McDonalds are providing a great service in times of pandemic such as making their worker keeping their physical appearance clean, keeping their POS always working, showing friendly gestures even they are wearing facemask by smiling with their eyes, assisting the customers to carry their food by following social distancing to keep the safety protocols running in the establishment. Showing that the workers are confident on the service they are providing even they are risking their lives. Keeping the delivery of their food on time, responding quickly when the customers need them, the quality of the service they have is excellent, the packaging of their food is properly packed, they manage to deliver the food with the appropriate temperature, maintaining the tempting smell of their product, and they are also strongly agreeing on the clean as you go practices. But not all the aspects they satisfy their customer at some point customers shows in the interpretation that there is a higher rating in the assurance for older people than younger in 25 years old. Gender and Marital status are not affected in rating of tangibility, reliability, responsiveness, assurance, and empathy they agreed that good quality of service has been served. Educational attainment has different insights in the responsiveness and empathy.

IX. RECOMMENDATION

To provide quality service in fast food restaurants they need to prioritize their customer. The restaurant managers should do maintain cleanliness and keep on welcoming ambiance once the customer enter the establishment. Hence, the researchers come up with a checklist as a guidance.

- checking the floor area every one hour
- keeping the barrier in the table clean, immediately bass out the dishes once the customer leaves the table

- Sanitize the area frequently right after the customer leaves the table this will help the table to be disinfected immediately.
- Teach your guard to greet customers who enter the facility this will make the customers feel that they are entering a friendly environment.
- Do not let your customer wait for too long before they are being served check on them every 5 minutes if they need something while they are waiting.

This will help both the customers and the management meet each other's expectation in doing a good service in time of pandemic. The researcher's recommendation for future researcher is.

- Conduct qualitative research to strengthen this research while following the safety protocols.
- Conduct research to other fast-food restaurant in Dasmariñas City, Cavite Philippines then made a comparison with this paper.
- Conduct a research paper about the service quality of these fast-food restaurants after pandemic.

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